

Appendix A: Background on AI Act Literature

The goal of this section is to provide the reader with a broader context related to the AIA. We outline the major steps of the legislative process, introduce relevant complementary material released by the European Commission, and provide a broad literature overview that extends beyond the engineering domain.

In terms of AIA-related literature, we need to be aware that the first major step in the legislative process was the initial proposal released by the European Commission in April 2021 [1]. The AIA entered into force on August 1, 2024, with the final text being published in the EU Official Journal on July 12, 2024 [2]. However, the final text was already available from June 13, 2024, just without the official regulation number assigned to it [3]. The preliminary-final text before the final lawyer-linguist check and formal endorsement by the Council was already available from March 13, 2024 [4].

Considering this timeline, it becomes clear that a significant part of the scientific literature is based on the initial proposal from April 2021 or some preliminary non-final version of the act. Various changes and adaptations were introduced during the legislative process until the final result. Especially the category of General Purpose AI (GPAI) models was not even part of the initial proposal from 2021 and underwent significant changes with the final version of the act that entered into force.

In 2025, the European Commission published (non-binding) guidelines with more context and interpretations on the definition of what constitutes an AI system [5]. Published and approved in the summer of 2025 [6], the Code of Practice [7] is another noteworthy addition to the AI Act, as it provides crucial guidance for what is necessary to demonstrate compliance with the AIA GPAI requirements.

In the following literature overview, we focus on works that are based on one of the (preliminary) final versions of the AIA (March 2024 or newer). This ensures that the state-of-the-art is reflected.

What can be found frequently in the current literature are discussions and analyses that are either on a more general level or focus on a more specific aspect of the regulation. A category of papers that was most popular during the early negotiation of the AIA, based on the 2021 proposal, is feedback-oriented works that include policy recommendations. Another common type of literature is relevance assessments for certain domains.

The category our contribution relates to is compliance-oriented papers that focus more on the operationalization of specific AIA aspects. This type of study has seen a considerable rise in recent times. We discuss it in the section about related work in the main paper.

In the following, we break these literature categories down in more detail and reference relevant exemplary literature.

1. AI Act Discussions and Analyses

To start, we look into the literature category of discussions and analyses. We present both papers that discuss the AIA on a rather general level, but also point to relevant studies that concern more specific AIA aspects. Moreira et al. [8] discussed the AIA in terms of transparent AI, with a special focus on Explainable AI (XAI). Relating to this, Borges [9] set out an in-depth discussion of the right to explanation of individual decision-making (Art 86). An article-specific focus was also followed by van Bekkum [10], who discussed AIA Article 10(5) that allows the processing of sensitive data for bias detection and correction purposes, but not for continuous bias monitoring.

A critical analysis of generative AI and copyright under the AIA was provided by Quintais [11]. Generative AI in terms of Large Language Models (LLM) was also the research focus of Lee et al. [12], who identified ethical risks and legal issues when using LLMs under the AIA. Genovesi et al. [13] conducted a comparative study about how AI Transparency is defined by different standards and guidelines, including the AIA. A general summary of the AIA with professionals in the software domain as their target audience was drawn up by Hermanns et al. [14].

Good general overviews and discussions of the AIA were done by Bellogín et al. [15] and Panetta and Tiani [16]. Ceyhun Necati Pehlivan et al. [17] provided a detailed reference guide for the AIA with detailed article-by-article legal commentary. They also set the AIA in a broader geographic context, considering regulatory developments around the world [18].

Cancela-Outeda [19] conducted a critical examination of the governance system that has been established by the AIA. Similarly, but from a more holistic perspective, Söderlund and Larsson [20] analyzed the enforcement design patterns of the AIA.

A recent publication by Palmiotto [21] analyzes the degree of fundamental right protection of the AIA and how it changed over the negotiation period.

Connecting to this, Barkane and Buka [22] evaluated the AIA’s fundamental rights protection by considering the prohibited AI practices that are set out in Article 5.

We can also find comparative analyses of the AIA with other laws. Musch et al. [23] compared the AIA and the General Data Protection Directive (GDPR), while Wörsdörfer [24] examined former US President Biden’s executive order on AI in comparison to the AIA. Górski and Ramakrishna [25] provided an interesting analysis of the right to an explanation between the AIA and the GDPR.

How the AIA facilitates trustworthy AI was analyzed by Ho and Caals [26]. When it comes to justice and fairness in AI development, Westerstrand [27] studied to what extent ethical AI development is covered by the AIA. Calero Valdez et al. [28] made a point about how the discipline of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) matters for the operationalization of the AIA.

2. AI Act Feedback and Policy Recommendations

Literature that focuses on providing feedback in the AIA and suggestions for improvement in the form of policy recommendations was popular during the act’s negotiation process and is therefore mostly connected to the initial AIA proposal from 2021. However, we can still find some recent papers of this category that are based on the final version of the regulation.

Greenstein and Zamboni [29] discussed the legislative dilemma when regulating emerging technologies. Legal uncertainties, inconsistencies, and general challenges of the AIA were highlighted. They propose a modified administrative model that is based on the idea of a dedicated EU AI Agency that should facilitate the balance between regulatory adaptability and legal certainty [29].

In a critical analysis of the AIA, Almada and Petit [30] highlighted that the AIA combines both product safety and fundamental rights protection, constituting a hybrid regulatory framework. The authors laid out challenges that emerge from the AIA’s design and proposed measures to mitigate these [30].

Rangone and Megale [31] studied risks connected to the use of AI in the domain of law and rulemaking that are currently not covered by the AIA. They end with policy recommendations that aim to tackle the identified risks feasibly [31].

A critical study of what is considered a *deep fake* under the AIA was carried out by Meding and Sorge [32]. The authors argued that the AIA’s definition of *deep fakes* and the associated obligations are not clear and precise enough. They set out policy recommendations that aim to mitigate the identified issues [32].

A taxonomy of a concept called “avoision” was provided by Yew et al. [33]. *Avoision* is a “[...] conduct that walks the line between legal avoidance and evasion — that firms might engage in so as to minimize the regulatory burden the AIA poses [33].” Policy recommendations were provided that aim to mitigate the *avoision* described in the study.

3. AI Act Relevance Assessments for Certain Domains

Next, we are looking into the AIA literature category of relevance assessments for certain domains. Several impact analyses were published for different domains: digital farming technologies by Ramon Ciutat [34], generative AI for the judiciary by Carnat [35], maritime autonomous surface ships by Lee et al. [36], AI for law enforcement by Sachoulidou [37], and e-commerce by Yaşar [38].

Piasecki et al. [39] provided a critical look at AI-generated journalism in an AIA context. The impact on AI-based crowd analysis was investigated by Veltmeijer and Gerritsen [40]. An interesting analysis was conducted by Sas [41], who laid out how the AIA’s GPAI category relates to generative non-player characters in video games.

The field with by far the most publications is the medical/healthcare domain. Solaiman and Malik [42] outlined limitations of the AIA in the context of evolving doctor-patient relationships when integrating AI into healthcare. More general impact analyses of the AIA on digital health, specifically related to the implications of the Medical Device Regulation (MDR), were provided by Djefal et al. [43], Aboy et al. [44], Quaranta and Amantea [45], and Kalodanis et al. [46]. Segate [47] looked at the regulatory implications for therapeutical smart cobotics.

But also more specific aspects within the medical domain were covered. Haden [48] explored the consequences of the AIA and the AI Liability Directive on medical negligence claims. A critical perspective on AI robotics in healthcare, questioning whether the MDR and the AIA adequately address this use case, was provided by Ebers [49]. AIA implications for the field of

neurotechnology were investigated by Bublitz et al. [50]. Finally, the AIA's implications for pharmaceutical AI deployers were covered by Murovec [51].

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